

Spectrophotometric Studies of the Ti(IV) Complex with N-Benzoyl N-*meta*-Sulphonatophenylhydroxylamine

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Like Fe(III), Ti(IV) also forms water soluble but yellow coloured complex with N-benzoyl-N-*meta*-sulphonatophenylhydroxylamine in the pH range 1.5-2.5. The absorbances were measured at 410 nm. The yellow complex obeys Beer's law from 4 to 14 ppm; the optimum range, as evaluated from the standard curve, being 5 to 14 ppm of Ti and the relative error, as calculated from the Ayres' equation is 2.72%. Due to the highly dissociated nature of the complex a large excess of the reagent is to be used for the spectrophotometric study and as a result the composition of the yellow complex could not be determined.

PREPARATION of N-benzoyl-N-*meta*-sulphonatophenylhydroxylamine and spectrophotometric studies of Fe(III) complexes with this reagent have been reported earlier¹. This reagent also forms water soluble Ti(IV), V(V) and U(VI) complexes. In this paper is reported an attempt made to study the Ti(IV) complex. It has also been noticed that Ti(IV) can be estimated in the presence of Fe(III) by masking it with ascorbic acid. Ti(IV) can also be estimated with sufficient accuracy in the presence of Fe(III) and V(V) with the use of NH₂OH, HCl or NH₂NH₂, H₂SO₄ as reducing agent.

Apparatus :

Optical densities were measured with a Hilger UVISPECK spectrophotometer using 1 cm. quartz cells against water as blank. The pH values of the solutions were measured with an 'Elico' pH meter (L 1-10).

Standard Ti(IV) solution :

A.R. potassium titanil oxalate was digested with (NH₄)₂SO₄ and concentrated H₂SO₄, boiled for 10-15 mins. allowed to cool, poured into a 500 ml measuring flask and diluted upto the mark. Its titanium content was then determined from an aliquot portion by precipitating with ammonia or by BPHA² (N-benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine) and igniting to oxide. The solution was afterwards diluted to give a solution containing 100 ppm of Ti.

Reagent and chemicals :

The reagent was prepared following the method previously described¹ and a 2.5% (w/v) solution of it was prepared in double distilled water. The reagent solution was found to decompose on keeping overnight; fresh solutions were therefore prepared before use.

Other chemicals used were either of A.R. quality or properly purified. Standard solutions of other

cations were prepared from their chlorides or sulphates and of anions from their sodium or potassium salts; the strengths were determined by standard methods.

10% HCl and 10% sodium acetate solution were used to adjust the pH values.

Absorbance curves :

Procedure : 2.5 cc Ti(IV) solution (100 ppm) was taken in a beaker and treated with 10 cc of reagent solution (2.5%). The pH of the solution was adjusted between 1.5 and 2.5 by adding in drops of 10% HCl and 10% sodium acetate solutions. It was then transferred into a 25 cc volumetric flask and diluted upto the mark. The optical density of the solution was then measured at the wavelengths of 360 nm to 450 nm against a reagent blank (Fig. 1). From the

Fig. 1 Absorption Curves of Ti(IV) Complex (Ti=10 ppm)

absorption curves it was observed that the absorbancy gradually increased from 450 nm to 360 nm but without any peak^{3,4} and hence in all subsequent studies absorbancy was measured at 410 nm since the reagent showed no absorption in this region.

Effect of pH and time :

The effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the formation of the Ti(IV) complex was studied at 410 nm for 10 ppm of Ti(IV) from pH 0.5 to 4.5 (Fig.2). The absorbancy of the Ti(IV) complex remained constant in the pH range 1.5 to 2.5. The colour was found to remain stable upto five hours.

Fig. 2 Effect of pH on the Ti(IV) complex (Ti = 10 ppm)

Fig. 3 Effect of reagent concentration on the Ti(IV) complex (Ti = 10 ppm) at pH = 2

Effect of reagent :

In this study 10 ppm of Ti(IV) solution were mixed with different amounts of reagent solutions (2.5% w/v) at pH = 2 (Fig. 3). It was observed that for the maximal colour development, the amount of the reagent should be as high as 50 times than the theoretical amount showing that the Ti(IV) complex is highly dissociated in nature and a large excess of the reagent can only influence the equilibrium to get the cent percent of complex formation. Due to this reason Job's method or the mole ratio method could not be applied to determine the composition of the Ti(IV) complex.

Beer's law, optimum range, accuracy and sensitivity :

The yellow Ti(IV) complex was found to obey Beer's law from 4 to 14 ppm of Ti at 410 nm in the pH range 1.5-2.5 with a large excess of the reagent (10 cc 2.5%). The optimum range, evaluated from the standard curve⁵, was found to be 5 to 14 ppm and the relative error per 1% absolute photometric error⁶ was 2.72%. The molecular extinction coefficient was found to be 1.584×10^3 . Spectrophotometric sensitivity, calculated according to Sandell⁷ was $0.0303 \mu\text{gm}/\text{cm}^2$.

Fig 4 (a) Beer's Law for the Ti(IV) complex at pH = 2

Effect of various ions :

To evaluate the tolerance limits for different ions, solutions containing 10 ppm of Ti and varying amounts of other ions were analysed as described under

absorbance studies. Absorbance errors above 0.005 were considered to indicate interference.

Fig. 4 (b) Standard curve for the Ti(IV) complex at pH=2

In this colour system Ag(I), V(V), Mo(VI), CrO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , F^- and EDTA interfere. However this system tolerates the presence of the following ions, the tolerance limits of which in ppm are given in parentheses : Mn^{2+} (200), Fe^{2+} (200), Zn^{2+} (200),

Cd^{2+} (200), Hg^{2+} (150), Al^{3+} (200), Sn^{2+} (150), Pb^{2+} (150), Bi^{3+} (100), Ce^{4+} (50), Th^{4+} (100), Cr^{3+} (20), Co^{2+} (30), Ni^{2+} (30) and Cu^{2+} (20). WO_4^{2-} can be tolerated in the presence of tartrate and Fe(III) in the presence of ascorbic acid. However Na^+ , K^+ , Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} do not interfere.

Estimation of Ti(IV) in the presence of Fe(III) and in the presence of Fe(III) and V(V) :

An aliquot solution containing Ti(IV) and Fe(III) or Ti(IV), Fe(III) and V(V) was taken in a 100 cc beaker. 2-3 cc of ascorbic acid (10%) was used to reduce Fe(III) but heated with 2-3 cc of hydroxylamine hydrochloride or hydrazine sulphate (10%) to reduce both Fe(III) and V(V). An excess (10 cc) of the reagent solution (2.5%) was added and the pH was adjusted in the range 1.5 to 2.5 with sodium acetate (10%), HCl(10%) or KOH(10%) as required. The solution was diluted upto 25 cc in a flask and the absorbancy was measured at 410 nm.

The Ti(IV)-Fe(III) system was found to tolerate upto 200 ppm of Fe(III) in the presence of 10 ppm of Ti(IV) with an error below 2.5% but the Ti(IV)-Fe(III)-V(V) system was found to tolerate upto 200 ppm of Fe(III) and 100 ppm of V(V).

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